

Vipin Richhariya

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Home: House No. - 143, Rua D João, São Paio , 4810-422 Guimarães (Portugal)

WORK EXPERIENCE

Centre for Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (CMEMS), University of Minho, Portugal – Guimarães , Portugal

City: Guimarães | Country: Portugal

Links <https://activities.esa.int/4000143019> | <https://activities.esa.int/4000143019> | <https://activities.esa.int/4000143019> | <https://activities.esa.int/4000143019> | <https://activities.esa.int/4000143019>

Recognised Researcher (ESA)

[20/01/2025 – Current]

- Development of 3D additive+subtractive laser powder bed fusion
- Enhancement of heat conductivity by introducing copper in Inconel
- The fabricated multimaterial innovation belongs to project "SpaceFuse" from the European Space Agency (ESA)

First Stage Researcher (BioInSole)

[01/10/2020 – 31/10/2024]

- Design and development of nanoparticle-reinforced-polymer for anti-slipping on ice under the project "BioInSole"
- Biomimicking of frog and gecko toepads using laser surface texturing
- Physical, chemical, and biological characterisation of produced silicone rubber composite
- Fabrication of state-of-the-art tribometer to determine the static and dynamic friction on wet and dry ice

PhD Researcher

[15/01/2021 – 14/01/2025]

- Design and development of multifunctional surfaces to control the frictional behaviour in the presence of ice
- Fabrication and characterisation of nature-inspired super-hydrophilic polymer structures to create mechanical interlocking with the help of capillary effect

First Stage Researcher

[20/05/2020 – 14/01/2021]

- Project "Comp4Ta" included the surface modification of Cu-Be alloy with diamond-based micro powder to reduce friction for glass blow moulding plungers
- Fabrication of the modified surface using hot isostatic pressing and engraving through laser surface texturing

First Stage Researcher

[20/11/2018 – 19/05/2020]

- Project "Friction - 0" focused on the effects of laser generated spherical dimples on the die steel to enhance lubricant's load carrying capacity
- Production, optimisation, characterisation, and ball-on-ring tests to analyse the effect of geometries and dimensions of dimples

 Centurion University – Bhubaneswar, India

City: Bhubaneswar | Country: India

Educator

[30/05/2015 – 01/09/2018]

- Intra-University Collaborative Tutoring for Competitive Examinations such as Graduate Aptitude Test in Engineering (GATE) and Indian Engineering Services (IES)

 ARMIET – Mumbai, India

City: Mumbai | Country: India

Assistant Professor

[17/06/2013 – 30/05/2015]

- Teaching responsibility of mechanical and civil undergraduates
- Fluid mechanics, thermal engineering, refrigeration and air-conditioning, metal cutting, advanced manufacturing process, power plant, industrial engineering and operations research, strength of materials, and design of structures
- Sports and Examination coordinator
- Admission in charge as a presenter to high-schoolers

 Energy Infratech Power Limited (EIPL) – New Delhi, India

City: New Delhi | Country: India

Design Engineer

[15/07/2008 – 14/07/2009]

- Auto CAD design of hydraulic power plant parts
- Survey of catchment area for turbine erection sites

EDUCATION AND TRAINING

PhD

University of Minho, Portugal [15/01/2021 – 17/03/2025]

City: Guimarães | Country: Portugal | Field(s) of study: Mechanical engineering & Surface engineering ; Materials Science ; Nano/micro reinforced polymers ; Biomimicry ; Laser surface modification and texturing ; Physical and chemical modification of surfaces to tailor the friction ; Additive+Subtractive manufacturing ; Multi-material, Multi-function, multi-physics | Final grade: Very Good | Level in EQF: EQF level 8 | NQF Level: Muito Bom | Thesis: Design and development of multifunctional surfaces to control the frictional behaviour in the presence of ice

Master of Technology (M.Tech)

National Institute of Technology (NIT) [15/07/2011 – 14/06/2013]

City: Rourkela | Country: India | Field(s) of study: Mechanical engineering specialised in production engineering ; Surface discharge coating of W-Cu on mild steel | Final grade: Very Good (A), 8.85/10 | Level in EQF: EQF level 7 | NQF Level: Honours (Portuguese Equivalence = 18/20) | Thesis: Surface Modification of AISI 1020 Mild Steel by Electrical Discharge Coating with Tungsten and Copper Mixed Powder Green Compact Electrodes"

Bachelor of Engineering (B.E.)

Technological University, Bhopal [15/11/2004 – 13/06/2008]

City: Gwalior | Country: India | Field(s) of study: Mechanical engineering | Final grade: 76.22% | Level in EQF: EQF level 6 | NQF Level: Honours (Portuguese Equivalence = 16/20)

Polytechnic Diploma

Government Polytechnic College, Nowgong [01/05/2002 – 01/12/2004]

City: Nowgong | Country: India | Field(s) of study: Mechanical Engineering | Final grade: 68.05% | Level in EQF: EQF level 5

LANGUAGE SKILLS

Mother tongue(s): Hindi | Bundeli

Other language(s):

English

LISTENING C2 READING C2 WRITING C1

SPOKEN PRODUCTION C2 SPOKEN INTERACTION C1

Portuguese

LISTENING A1 READING A2 WRITING A1

SPOKEN PRODUCTION A1 SPOKEN INTERACTION A1

Levels: A1 and A2: Basic user; B1 and B2: Independent user; C1 and C2: Proficient user

SKILLS

Designing and Fabrication / Laser Surface Texturing / Surface engineering / Tribology tests / Biomimetics / Knowledge of vulcanization machines / Polymer Nanocomposite / Polymer Composites / Additive Manufacturing (3D printing) / Hot Pressing / Additive+Subtractive Manufacturing / Surface Characterization / Excellent knowledge of Mechanical Engineering Subjects / Basic COMSOL skills / Good knowledge of OriginLab Software / EZCAD / Minitab (Basic) / Basic Knowledge of Civil Engineering Subjects / LaTeX / Public Speaking / Storytelling

HONOURS AND AWARDS

[09/12/2024] American Chemical Society Press Release

Idea of Excellence for Publication

[30/05/2022] IMFAHE Foundation, Boston

Best Oral Presentation

[07/12/2012] National Institute of Technology, Rourkela - India

Sports Fiesta Cricket Championship Award

[25/01/2013] NIT, Rourkela - India

Cricket Championship Award for Captaining the Winning Team

[31/10/2025] National Institute of Technology, Trichy - India

National Cricket Championship for National Institute of Technology Group Sports Meet

[30/12/1997] Government School of Excellence, Nowgong - India

Cultural Educational Examination

NETWORKS AND MEMBERSHIPS

India

Lifetime Member of Indian Society for Technical Education (ISTE)

Portugal

Elsevier Reviewer

Portugal

Physica Scripta Journal Reviewer

HOBBIES AND INTERESTS

Literature, Movies, Theatre, Music, Storytelling I am a poet with two decades of experience in English and Hindi and an aspiring novelist currently working on a philosophical novel. Alongside literature, I enjoy cinema across genres from art-house films and documentaries to science fiction, biographies, and historical dramas. Avid reading,

writing, and films all inspire me as forms of storytelling that explore human experiences, provoke thought, and deepen cultural understanding.

PROJECTS

[20/01/2025 – Current]

SpaceFuse Collaboration among ESA, University of Twente, Netherlands, and University of Minho, Portugal

[01/10/2020 – 31/10/2024]

BioInSole Ranked first among 267 national project on promotional application based FCT - Portugal awards

[20/05/2020 – 14/01/2021]

Comp4Ta Collaboration between University of Minho and University of Coimbra

[20/11/2018 – 19/05/2020]

Friction - 0 Collaboration between University of Minho and University of Coimbra, Portugal

CONFERENCES AND SEMINARS

[16/09/2024 – 19/09/2024] Warsaw University of Technology, Poland

EMRS - 2024 A Superhydrophilic Biomimicked Ceramic-Reinforced-Polymer Nanocomposite for Enhanced Slip Resistance and Adhesion

[18/06/2023 – 21/06/2023] Caesars Palace, Las Vegas, USA

PowderMet/AMPM A Nature-Inspired Superhydrophilic Nano-Powder based Silicone Rubber Composite

[19/07/2022 – 22/07/2022] University of Coimbra, Portugal

Junior Euromat Anti-slipping winter shoe-soles: A nature inspired solution

[30/05/2022 – 30/05/2022] Boston, USA

IMFAHE Foundation (Online) A nature-inspired slip-resistant winter shoe-sole

[05/05/2022 – 06/05/2022] University of Porto, Portugal

EM - 2022 An innovative moulding method for anti-slipping shoe-soles

[10/04/2022 – 13/04/2022] Marina Grande, Portugal

Materials Processing, MDPI (Abstract Publication) - Laser Machining of Zirconia Green Compacts to Produce Cavities and Blocks: Parametric Optimization and Patterning- Laser Surface Texturing of Stainless-Steel Cutlery to Integrate Ceramic Blocks: Parametric Optimization and Patterning

[28/06/2021 – 29/06/2021] University of Porto, Portugal

DCE - 2021 - A bio-inspired Anti-slipping Winter Shoe-sole- Nature inspired wet adhesive E-skin patch for biosensing applications

[18/05/2019 – 18/05/2019] University of Minho, Portugal

BiomatDevices Organisation Committee Member

PUBLICATIONS

Capillary-enhanced biomimetic adhesion on icy surfaces for high-performance anti-slip shoe-soles

Journal Name: ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces

Vipin Richhariya, Ashis Tripathy, Oscar Carvalho, Jose Gomes, Md Julker Nine, and F. S. Silva (2024)

Unravelling the physics and mechanisms behind slips and falls on icy surfaces.....

Journal Name: Elsevier Materials & Design

Vipin Richhariya, Ashis Tripathy, Oscar Carvalho, Md Julker Nine, Dusan Losic, and F. S. Silva (2023)

An Experimental Parametric Optimisation for Laser Engraving and Texturing to Integrate.....

Journal Name: Materials, MDPI

Vipin Richhariya, Georgina Miranda, and Filipe Samuel Silva (2024)

A Review of Hybrid Manufacturing: Bridging Additive and Subtractive Technologies

Journal Name: Materials, MDPI

Bruno Freitas, Vipin Richhariya, Mariana Silva, António Vaz, Sérgio Lopes, Óscar Carvalho (2025)

Manufacture and mechanical-tribological assessment of diamond-reinforced Cu-based coatings.....

Journal Name: Tribology International, Elsevier

E. Frutos, V. Richhariya, F. S. Silva, and B. Trindade (2023)

Effect of carbon nanotubes on the tribological behavior of PEEK- based composites.....

Journal Name: Engineering Research Express, IOP Science

Taina Pigosso, Vipin Richhariya, Cristiano Binder, Filipe S. Silva, Oscar Carvalho, and J. R. Gomes (2022)

Tribological performance of laser-textured steel surfaces in unidirectional sliding.....

Journal Name: Lubrication Science, Wiley

Pedro J. Amoroso, Amilcar Ramalho, Vipin Richhariya, and Filipe S. Silva, Albano Cavaleiro (2021)

Synergic effect of TMD coating on textured steel using micro-EDM

Journal Name: Surface and Coatings Technology, Elsevier

Sharma, P., Mahadeshwara, M.R., Vilhena, L., Richhariya, V., Silva, F., Ramalho, A., Carvalho, S. and Cavaleiro, A. (2023)

Polymeric structure and its applications (Patented from Portugal (EU)119649 PP 2024.08.09)

Authors: Vipin Richhariya and Filipe Samuel Silva

Capillary Dynamics Analysis of Millimetric Tubes for Anti-Slip Surfaces: A Phase-Field Based Finite Element Approach and Experimental Validation

Journal Name: Advanced Theory And Simulations, Wiley

Shivam Sharma, Vipin Richhariya, Diana Pinho, Óscar Carvalho, Filipe S. Silva, Ashis Tripathy, Nuno Dourado, and Susana O. Catarino (2025)